

USE OF VIDEO MATERIALS IN THE IMPROVEMENT OF VISUAL AND AUDITORY SKILLS IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract. *This article defines the role of a modern teacher in the era of high technology. It can be seen that today the foreign language teacher plays a decisive role in the organization of the educational process. Because it is the teacher who determines the goals, tasks, methods and organizational bases of teaching, and chooses appropriate textbooks and training manuals. For these reasons this article talks about the use of video materials in the improvement of visual and auditory skills of the advanced stage of language learning.*

Keywords: *experience, distribute, instructing role, function, language learning, video materials, coherence, usefulness, influence, comprehensibility, understanding, listening, auditory skill, visual skill.*

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ВИДЕОМАТЕРИАЛОВ В СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИИ ЗРИТЕЛЬНЫХ И СЛУХОВЫХ НАВЫКОВ В ИЗУЧЕНИИ ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *В данной статье определяется роль современного учителя в эпоху высоких технологий. Видно, что сегодня учитель иностранного языка играет решающую роль в организации учебного процесса. Потому что именно учитель определяет цели, задачи, методы и организационные основы обучения, выбирает соответствующие учебники и учебные пособия. По этим причинам в данной статье рассказывается об использовании видеоматериалов в совершенствовании зрительных и слуховых навыков на продвинутом этапе изучения языка.*

Ключевые слова: *опыт, распространение, обучающая роль, функция, изучение языка, видеоматериалы, связность, полезность, влияние, понятность, понимание, слушание, слуховой аппарат, зрительный аппарат.*

INTRODUCTION

As we know, learning foreign languages is important in today's developing world. It is natural that learning different methods is an important factor for us in language learning, and many studies are currently being conducted in this regard.

The analysis shows that watching video materials is enough to develop listening and visual skills in English. However, insufficient pedagogical methods have been developed in this regard, and this field has not been sufficiently studied. Therefore, it is important to conduct scientific practical research on the use of video materials, analysis and justification of its positive aspects and results in the improvement of listening skills in language learning.

Literature analysis. During the analysis, compared to the control group, which was exposed to the passive learning process in English (i.e., only the educational materials), it was found that the amount of knowledge acquired by residents who participated in active teaching based on audiovisual technologies was significantly higher.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Video materials were taken as an object of research. The analysis of the processes of using video materials in improving listening skills in English language learning was carried out based on the literature on the topic and the results of previous scientific works [8, 583].

Educational technology represents a system of influencing the listener during the educational process. It involves the management of the didactic process, which includes the stages of audience activity, organization and control. The problem of effectiveness of educational technology is based on the strategies of presentation, acquisition, storage, reproduction and actualization of various forms of educational information. This article examines audiovisual technologies (AT) for foreign language teaching in secondary schools [1, 158].

It contains information about a number of audiovisual activities for teaching a foreign language. The study provides some insights into students' perception of video in the learning process. Classification of video materials allows consideration of various pedagogical and didactic conditions of the implementation of audiovisual technology. The functional features of the video film and the four stages of audiovisual educational technology based on the video film are described in the educational process. To demonstrate the learning process, viewing objectives include illustrative viewing, fact finding, learning, critical, and searching. Pedagogical algorithms based on the structure of the knowledge acquisition process in accordance with the stages of AT implementation (prevision) have been developed (presentation, post-vision actualization) and these are reviewed [10, 182].

An educational intervention using AT will be developed, and we will examine (1) the effectiveness of audiovisual technology as a teaching method and (2) the level of acquisition of proposed language content knowledge. The purpose of teaching students a foreign language is to form and develop communicative competence of a foreign language, which includes various skills, abilities and knowledge of grammar, pronunciation and vocabulary, reading, writing, listening and speaking skills.

When assessing the level of communicative competence, we used the calculation of the knowledge acquisition coefficient of the educational material, in which a significant improvement was observed. In foreign language acquired knowledge and AT was perceived as effective in foreign language teaching. AT was adopted to facilitate student learning and encourage active learning. AT-based foreign language teaching has a positive effect on students' performance and should play a leading role in the formation and development of effective communicative competence.

The problem of the effectiveness of educational technology is related to the problem of strategies for expressing, acquiring, storing and reproducing various forms of educational information. The problem of human and information interaction in the educational process is related to the problem of the effectiveness of modern educational technologies. Formalization of educational technology of pedagogical activities allows to repeat the successful experience of teachers. Educational technology represents a specific way of interacting with educational information. This question has been widely discussed in the literature. Different aspects of knowledge transfer methodology in educational systems have been studied by scholars in different contexts [3, 255].

There are many articles and books on the problem of knowledge transfer. One of them, the ideas of V. I. Vernadsky's articles are of the greatest importance in the era of integration of enormous knowledge accumulated by mankind. Now the integration processes predicted by V. I. Vernadsky have become a reality. They will become the basis of the fourth scientific revolution. Moreover, their advancement in all aspects, especially in the field of education, is not only

urgent, but also natural. Therefore, the expediency of using natural interaction processes in the informative experience of cognitive structures in the field of the triple approach in education (text-image-meaning, rational-emotional-intuitive, etc.) was demonstrated [4, 214].

Examining this interaction allows for the identification of additional resources of well-known learning strategies and technologies. One of the main requirements for the effectiveness of any activity is to create favorable psychological conditions for it. Visualization plays an important role in this process. At the same time, in modern educational activities, teachers' attention to the figurative-emotional sphere of the audience is insufficient. In the theory of teaching, the idea of moving from explanatory and illustrative pedagogy to a structurally new direction serves as an incentive to introduce visualization into the educational process [13, 162].

The introduction of visualization leads to the creation of a learning environment that is considered psychologically more comfortable and safer for the trainee. Thus, the problem of modernization of the humanities can be solved by creating a simple, reliable and effective model of interaction between the teacher, the audience, the studied subject and the subjects. To solve this problem, a set of didactic tools representing a system including visual tools was considered. It helps to generalize and remember the learned material, which helps to keep it in memory longer and to reproduce it easily [11, 885].

The main idea of this article is to bring a general sense of humanistic thinking to the field of video-based foreign language teaching according to some simple principles:

- the student is the center of the educational process as an actor, executor;
- video creator and translator;
- the entire educational process is organized for the student and is aimed at forming and developing the communicative competence of a foreign language;
- the teacher offers the student different types of video resources in different forms and stages;
- they are selected by the teacher and processed for use in the educational process;
- the operative part of audiovisual technologies is implemented through pedagogical algorithms;
- their choice is determined by the goals of the educational process;
- since students (and teachers) are very different from each other, they should be provided with a wide range of activities and incentives;
- all text is produced by the students, and while viewing, they create their own, internal version of what is on the screen;
- when filming, they make all decisions both behind and in front of the lens;
- even coursebook material can be given life by allowing students to absorb and reconstruct it in their own way;
- experimental studies have shown the effectiveness of using audiovisual technologies in the educational process.

RESEARCH RESULTS

According to the results of the analysis, our study is the first example of the use of audiovisual technologies as a system of teaching a foreign language in a secondary school. According to the analysis, compared to the control group, which was exposed to the passive learning process (i.e., only educational materials), it was shown that the amount of knowledge

gained was significantly higher in residents who participated in active learning based on audiovisual technologies. The residents were also satisfied with the content and format of the training. All of them have been mentioned above.

DISCUSSION

As can be seen from the above examples, in general, this study shows that audiovisual technologies can contribute to the effective teaching of a foreign language as part of the high school humanities curriculum. We briefly discussed the problem of using video in the educational process. We have successively focused on different types and forms of video data:

- video films,
- video data
- self-made video and more.

In addition, this study made it possible to highlight the main features of different types of videos used in the process of foreign language teaching.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the experience of teaching with video meets the expected results and clearly confirms the application and use of video in education. Our future goal is the wider use and further development of audiovisual technologies in teaching foreign languages. Further development of a humanistic environment and its effective coexistence with existing traditional teaching aids requires different approaches and cooperation. Our past experiences and current trends in the field of audio-visual technologies clearly define and determine our future directions and activities in this field. The current situation in teaching foreign languages should encourage us to conduct more research on audiovisual technologies, to develop new algorithms and tasks to improve the effectiveness of teaching foreign languages.

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